

D3.4

EMPOWER

deliverables

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Eye-Tracking Module

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System components needed to get eye-tracking data from devices to be used as an input for the platform games, as well as interfaces with WP4.

Description

WP.3

Work Package. 3

Lead Beneficiary – (UV)

Eye-tracking Module

Description of the Eye-tracking Module

System components are needed to get eye-tracking data from devices to be used as input for the platform games and interfaces with WP4.

Date	Version	Description	Authors
29.09.2023	1.0	First version	Attila Kovari, Jozsef Katona, Are Daehlen, Ilona Heldal, Jerry Chun-Wei Lin, Abdul Rehman Javed
17.01.2024	1.1	Updated version	Attila Kovari

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#1. Introduction

The Eye-tracking (ET) Module will be used for considering the children's eye gaze data and visual focus during games-based testing to examine the children's cognitive behaviour. The focus is that the gaze data provided by the ET Module allows connecting the eye gaze parameters with emotion-based parameters and analysing these data (WP4).

#2. ET Module preliminaries and specification

Before starting the development, we took the following aspects into account:

- The most used eye-tracking devices manufactured by Tobii for both research and other purposes.
- In our experience, the Tobii eye-tracking devices are the best if the head moves during the test, which a Tobii expert also confirmed at a presentation.
- In most cases, 5-point calibration is used for gaze calibration.
- Based on the preliminary literature review, there is no unique detailed specification for the eye-tracking system for disabled children.

ET MODULE SPECIFICATION

ET device: Tobii Pro Nano eye-tracker hardware

ET device placement: the holder provided by the manufacturer for the ET device is used (under screen position). The order of the ET device above the screen must also be examined because this placement is preferable for a touch screen (the hand may cover the device).

Eye and head position calibration: the commonly used solutions were selected for these calibrations. The head position calibration screen can adjust the head to the correct position. The head is visualised using head/eye icons and indicates that actual position is right or wrong. For the eye gaze position calibration, the standard 5-point calibration is used.

Interfaces: The ET Module provides head and eye gaze calibrations, which need two user interfaces: head position and gaze point calibration screens.

Provided data: left and right gaze position on the screen, left and suitable pupil diameter, and head position. Using these raw data, the additional feature extraction of general eye

movement parameters (like fixations and saccades) is implemented as part of the WP4 platform algorithms.

#2. ET Module demonstration

If the ET data recording is started, it runs in the background and collects the data, and at the end of the test, the recorded raw data is stored in the MariaDB database. The platform game starts and stops the ET data recording and has access to real-time data. The central element of the system is the Tobii Software Development Kit (SDK), which manages the Tobii Pro Nano device and calibration and provides access to the raw gaze data. The system architecture is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 System architecture

The ET Module has two interfaces' head and eye gaze calibrations. These interfaces are presented in the following.

During the head calibration, by moving the position of the head, the head/eye icon on the screen also moves, and the appropriate place is indicated by a green background (Figure 2). While the position is imperfect, the background changes red depending on the degree of deviation from the correct position (Figure 3).

Figure 2 Head calibration screen - acceptable

Figure 3 Head calibration screen - inadequate

Usually, the standard calibration process shows 5 (or 9) points to get a helpful calibration that works in most areas of the screen (Figure 4). This was also implemented in the ET Module (Figure 5).

Figure 4 5-point gaze position calibration

Figure 5 Implemented 5-point calibration (green: good, yellow: acceptable, red: wrong)

The recorded raw eye-tracking data is stored in the MariaDB database (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Raw gaze data stored in the MariaDB database.

id	id_activity	id_session	PosX	PosY	PupilDiaX	PupilDiaY	HeadX	HeadY	HeadZ	Tim
170	101	1011	135,694	11,4419	1,97555	1,93147	-7,41558	-7,41667	599,104	
169	101	1011	692,802	687,799	2,10474	2,05792	-6,74467	-5,22107	598,28	
168	101	1011	692,409	700,422	2,10268	2,0614	-6,8173	-5,21579	597,991	
167	101	1011	694,986	698,354	2,10559	2,03864	-6,88541	-5,15621	597,89	
166	101	1011	692,396	686,479	2,11966	2,05211	-6,95114	-5,06573	597,839	
165	101	1011	699,352	690,75	2,11534	2,04857	-7,01828	-5,01347	597,787	
164	101	1011	711,099	676,823	2,10419	2,05763	-7,06038	-4,94028	597,941	

#3. Pilot Feedback and Interventions on ET Module

Two pilots were conducted in Romania and Portugal in May and June of 2023.

ROMANIAN PILOT

Place: Constanța

1. Date: May 22nd - May 26th

Feedbacks:

- 1, Hand positioning of users occludes the eye-tracker. The problem relates to the touch-based interaction method and the ET device positioned at the bottom of the screen.
- 2. The calibration experience was boring for most children. During the process, they sometimes look away from the screen or get distracted by something else. This negatively affects the collected eye-tracking data.
- 3. The standard 5-point calibration was too fast for most children. 2-3 rounds of recalibration were needed to get satisfactory calibration results.
- 4. The calibration process was repeated after every level of the game. This resulted in some children being bored/annoyed with how many times they had to calibrate, leading to worse calibration results further into the tests.
- 5. The database solution needed to split sessions for each participant adequately. This required creating a new database for each user to be able to separate the data.
- 6, Head positioning guidelines only provided changes in the background colour to assist in creating proper head positioning (green = good, red = bad). It would also be ideal to have text guidance to help teachers understand what is wrong and what is needed for proper head positioning.
- 7, Distance requirements for the eye-tracker were challenging for some children, as their arms were shorter and could not reach the screen.
- 8, Calibration required the detection of both eyes to begin. One participant could not open one of their eyes, forcing us to skip calibration and ET data collection.

Modifications:

- 1. Placement of the ET device above the screen gives uncertain operation and is not recommended by the manufacturer. As a result, this placement is not applicable. Unique Tobii holders may be too expensive.
- 2, Additional animation during the eye gaze calibration: the calibration point pulses, the calibration is in two stages at each point, the more attention-grabbing yellow colour is used.
- 3. The speed of calibration has been slowed down.
- 4. No ET Module problem.
- 5, ET Module database integration issues were solved. This includes a fix to the database session issue.
- 6. We have modified the calibration screen and used a head pictogram to visualise the actual head position.
- 7, Hardware limitations. Special Tobii holders may solve this problem, but this is too expensive.
- 8. If it's important, then we will investigate.

PORTUGAL PILOT

Place: Lisbon

Date: June 5-16, 2023

Feedbacks:

- In the case of the Portuguese pilot, a computer mouse was used during the attention game, where eye tracking was used. As a result, the problem of covering the eye movement tracking device did not occur.
- During the head and eye calibration, no significant problems appeared; presumably, the children tested were of a different nature. Recalibration was only necessary in a few cases.
- The technical problems that arose during the pilot in Romania were resolved, so they no longer occurred.

Modifications:

- No specific intervention

Post evaluation of recorded data: summarise the raw data and the feature extracted eye parameters. The review confirmed the ET Module's functionality (number of data, eye parameters, heatmaps). The recorded data can be found in the WP3-Deliverables\Prototype Application\ Portugal_ETdata_evaluation.xlsx file.

#4. ET Module prototype

The ET Module unit package prototype can be found in:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1mowbgZFquFwJnY7AQ8McwPmRuPlamI8P>

Tobii Pro Nano eye-tracker hardware, Windows 10 or 11 operating system, and Tobii Eye Tracker Manager must be installed and set up to use eye movement tracking during games.

ET documentation 2023.09.22.docx contains detailed information about the use of the Module.